

BABOTS

Horizon Europe 101098722

*BABOTS:
The design and control of small swarming
biological animal robots*

RP1 Quality assessment reports

Deliverable Number.: D25
Deliverable N. Relative to WP: D6.7
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Contact Authors: Elio Tuci (UNamur)
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Duration: 48 months
Project Coordinator: UNamur (Belgium)
Beneficiaries: HUJI (Israel),
CNR-ISTC (Italy),
MPG (Germany),
AALTO (Finland),
ZERO SRL (Italy)

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1 Introduction

The main aim of this document is to illustrate the activity concerning the quality assessment of the project during the period April-September 2024. The activity of the quality assessment during the first six months of the project (October-March 2024) has been illustrated in Deliverable D22 (D6.4). As discussed in D22, the BABOTS project quality assessment is carried out using a spreadsheet in which each WP leader can signal any issue that impacts both the dissemination, communication, and exploitation, and the work plan, including delays on expected deadlines and the emergence of unexpected risks. The issues raised by the WP leaders are first processed by the project coordinator and if needed, discussed by the entire consortium either by emails or during project meetings. Each spreadsheet covers a three months period and its end date falls closely to a project meeting (either in presence or online). This allows the consortium to discuss during the meeting any issue signalled in the corresponding spreadsheet.

This document briefly illustrates the Quality Assessment exercise II covering the period April-June 2024 (see section 2 and the document attached) and the Quality Assessment exercise III covering the period July-September 2024 (see section 3 and the document attached).

2 Quality Assessment exercise II (April-June 2024)

The majority of the issues in this exercise concerns the activity of WP3. These issues have been entirely discussed during the project meeting held in Rome at the end of May 2024. To improve the communication and interaction between the partners, several Discord channels have been activated. These channels are meant to facilitate the discussion and the exchange of ideas and readings between the members of the project working on WP3. The consortium acknowledges that the activity on T3.3 has started earlier than planned without any negative consequence on the overall work-plan. Moreover, to facilitate the emergence of collaboration and for the smooth interaction between the biological and modelling side of the project, the consortium decided during the meeting in Rome (May 2024), to organise a first meeting between young researches to be held in Bonn in September 2024.

During the meeting in Rome, the consortium acknowledged that the problems with the OpenAire platform do not allow: i) to update the project site on OpenAire with the latest documents (both reports and scientific documents); and ii) to automatically transfer documents resulted from the dissemination of scientific activity directly into the EU portal on the continuous reporting section and on the project website at www.babots.eu. Since these problems were meant to be temporary and resolved within a reasonable delay, the consortium decided not to take any alternative actions for the time being, waiting for OpenAire to recover full functionality. The OpenAire status is reconsidered during the project September 2024 online meeting.

3 Quality Assessment exercise III (July-September 2024)

During summer 2024, the leader of WP1 signals few potential delays in the activity of T1.1 and T1.3 that may have had an impact on the activity of WP2. During the project meeting held in

September 2024, the consortium acknowledged that the scientific activity has been progressing as expected. Thus, these issues related WP1 have been marked as resolved. In a similar way, the delays emerged during the summer concerning the work of T2.1 have been considered resolved. The difficulties in hiring qualified personnel have been initially overcome with the support of non-specialised personnel (like lab technicians). During the September 2024 meeting, the consortium acknowledged that, in spite of these difficulties, personnel has been hired in all labs. The issue with the OpenAire has been resolved. OpenAire recovered its full functionality during the summer 2024.

For what concerns dissemination and communication activities, during the September meeting, the project coordinator has informed the project partners that he has been invited to participate at a workshop in Portugal titled "Bio-inspired Technologies and Smart Materials" and organised in the framework of the EU-funded project FORGING that aims to promote the uptake by industry and society of innovative tech solutions that represent not only industrial or economic opportunities, but also have a positive impact in society and environment. The project coordinator has accepted to participate online to this workshop, due to personal issues that currently limit his possibility to travel abroad. The organiser (i.e., representative of APRE - Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea) expected only an in-person attendance. Thus, the participation of the project coordinator to this event has been cancelled. The representative of APRE promised to re-invite members of the BABOTS project to other similar events in the future.

Project Quality Review	
Project Acronym:	BABOTS
Project Coordinator:	Elio Tuci
Review Date:	30/6/2024
N. Exercise	2
Overall Score:	98%

WP	Score	% Quality Compliance	Included?
WP1	250	100.00%	Yes
WP2	250	100.00%	Yes
WP3	185	88.10%	Yes
WP4	250	100.00%	Yes
WP5	250	100.00%	Yes
WP6	245	98.00%	Yes

Area	Average Score	Average % Quality Compliance	Included?
Scope	49.17	98.33%	Yes
Schedule	47.50	95.00%	Yes
Cost	28.33	100.00%	Yes
Quality	28.33	100.00%	Yes
Risk	36.67	100.00%	Yes
Communication	48.33	96.67%	Yes

Overall key assessment	
<60%	Critical /significant issues or major process non-compliance.
60% < ... < 90%	Unless immediate action is taken, project may become red.
>90%	No significant non-compliance foreseeable at this time.

Scoring legend		
No	Nothing done or no answer	0
Not much	Something done, but very limited	2.5
Partially	Some work done, but not to the required/expected level	5
To a great extent	Most work done, requires little more effort	7.5
Yes	Work done according to program	10
N/A	This check is not applicable to this project	-

ID	Findings	Impact	Recommendation	Action Details (effort & responsible)
1	WP3 - Q5	Progress in T3.1 and T3.3	Clearly explain the deviation from start time	This will be done in the first technical report RP1.
2	WP3 - Q5	Task schedule	There has been a suggestion to better define task schedule in the future.	The suggestion is sound. A more detailed schedule for tasks will be defined during the next meetings that will take place Online in september 2024.
3	WP3 - Q8 and Q9	Monitoring activity in T3.1 and T3.3	Focus attention to potential deviation to original schedule	The earliest check will be conducted in September 2024 in which the WP leader will be asked to report on activities timeline and work progress.
4	WP3 - Q21	Communication and interactions between partners involved in WP3	A request for better and more frequent interactions is made	This point will be definitely discussed during the September 2024 meeting. However, to improve on this aspect a in person meeting between PhD and PostDoc working on the project has been already scheduled for mid-september 2024 in Bonn. This should significantly help to improve the interactions between the partners on specific WPs issues.
5	WP3 - Q22	Meetings only at project level	A request for meetings in which people can discuss only specific WPs related issues is made	To solve this issue, the meeting in Bonn scheduled for mid-september 2024 between young researchers working on the project should significantly help to overcome this issue. In this meeting, the researchers will also discuss and identify ways to improve the interactions among them on specific WPs related issues.
6	WP6- Q9	Documents not correctly transferred from Zenodo to the continuous reporting section due to problems with OpenAire	OpenAire is under re-constuction. The consortium expect that this problem will be resolved as soon as the functionalities of OpenAire are reactivated.	The consortium decided to wait to before taking any further action to see the evolution of the works on the OpenAire portal. The issue will be re-evaluated in September.
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WP1 WP Leader Monika Scholz		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP2 WP Leader Serena Ding		Quality Compliance			Comments
		Answer	Score	Percentage	
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP3 WP Leader Vito Trianni		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	45	90.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Partially	5		We should better document that the tasks related to T3.3 are starting earlier, and why. Also, there has been not much work on T3.1, and we are now catching up considering the new plans made during the meeting in Rome.
Schedule		0	40	80.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Partially	5		There is no real timeline, but activities are carried out at a satisfactory pace. This is mainly due to the initial stage of the project, in which explorations are being conducted. It would be advisable to have some more detailed per-task planning in the future, especially for the RP2 and RP3.
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	To a great extent	7.5		Tasks have long durations that allow compensating possible delays. T3.1 started later than expected, while T3.3 started earlier. These deviations should be carefully monitored.
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	To a great extent	7.5		The lack of a precise timeline does not allow to track progress. However, all activities are documented.
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		1	20	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	N/A	-		
Quality		1	20	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	N/A	-		
Risk		2	20	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	N/A	-		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	N/A	-		
Communication		0	40	80.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Partially	5		So far there has been little interaction, mainly due to warm-up phase. We expect communication to improve in the forthcoming periods.
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Partially	5		Meetings only at project-wide level
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		4	185	88.1%	

WP4 WP Leader Matti Häyry		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP5 WP Leader Ithai Rabinowitch		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP6 WP Leader Elio Tuci		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	45	90.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Partially	5		Due to problems related to the functioning of the OpenAire website, the documents concerning the reporting and those related to the scientific activity of dissemination are not correctly transferred from the repository Zenodo to the project EU portal in the continuous reporting section.
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	245	98.0%	

Project Quality Review	
Project Acronym:	BABOTS
Project Coordinator:	Elio Tuci
Review Date:	30/9/2024
N. Exercise	3
Overall Score:	97%

WP	Score	% Quality Compliance	Included?
WP1	240	96.00%	Yes
WP2	243	97.00%	Yes
WP3	205	89.13%	Yes
WP4	250	100.00%	Yes
WP5	250	100.00%	Yes
WP6	250	100.00%	Yes

Area	Average Score	Average % Quality Compliance	Included?
Scope	49.17	98.33%	Yes
Schedule	45.83	91.67%	Yes
Cost	30.00	100.00%	Yes
Quality	28.33	100.00%	Yes
Risk	37.92	98.61%	Yes
Communication	48.33	96.67%	Yes

Overall key assessment	
<60%	Critical /significant issues or major process non-compliance.
60% < ... < 90%	Unless immediate action is taken, project may become red.
>90%	No significant non-compliance foreseeable at this time.

Scoring legend		
No	Nothing done or no answer	0
Not much	Something done, but very limited	2.5
Partially	Some work done, but not to the required/expected level	5
To a great extent	Most work done, requires little more effort	7.5
Yes	Work done according to program	10
N/A	This check is not applicable to this project	-

ID	Findings	Impact	Recommendation	Action Details (effort & responsible)
1	WP1 - Q7	Potential delays on dependencies between WP1 and WP2	Issue resolved	This issue, raised in summer 2024, has been discussed during the 19/9/2024 online project meeting. The consortium agree that, in view of the progress made in WP1, this issue can be considered resolved.
2	WP2 - Q2	Potential delays in T2.1	Issue resolved	This issue, raised in summer 2024, has been discussed during the 19/9/2024 online project meeting. The consortium agree that, in view of the progress made in T2.1, this issue can be considered resolved.
3	WP2 - Q7	Delays on T2.1 impact T2.2	Issue resolved	Issue discussed on 19/9/2024 project meeting and resolved.
4	WP2 - Q8	Difficulties in hiring qualified researchers	Issue persist	The delays generated by difficulties in hiring sufficiently qualified researchers for the work in WP2 has been overcome with the support of non-specialist personnel.
5	WP3 - Q5	T3.1 starts earlier	This issue has no negative impact on the work plan	During the 19/9/2024 online project meeting, the consortium agreed that this issue will be discussed and justified in the description of the activities on WP3 detailed in the first technical report due to M13. This will be done by the WP3 leader.
6	WP3 - Q22	Need of more interactions between the biologist and the modelling side of the project to facilitate the work in WP3	The consortium agrees that this is an important point. More resources will be invested to facilitate the interaction and the cooperation between the biological and the modelling side of the project.	On the 16-18/9/2024 a meeting has been held in Bonn at MPG-NB between the young researchers of the project. A report on the activities carried out during this meeting has been done at the 19/9/2024 at the online project meeting by one researcher. The entire consortium agrees that this meeting has been absolutely beneficial to improve cooperation and coordination between WP1, WP2 and WP3. Thus, another meeting of similar type will take place in MPG-AB before the end of the 2024. The details of this meeting will be discussed and defined in October by the leaders of WP2 and WP3.
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WP1 WP Leader Monika Scholz		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		Changes and alternative approaches are discussed and documented
Schedule		0	42.5	85.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Partially	5		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	To a great extent	7.5		Due to earlier delays (see first report), some external dependencies (WP2) may be affected
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	47.5	95.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	To a great extent	7.5		Meetings have been held in line with consortium meetings and additional meetings at conferences.
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	240	96.0%	

WP2 WP Leader Serena Ding		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	47.5	95.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	To a great extent	7.5		The realistic odor gradients were delayed to part availability and have delayed the virtual gradient work by a few months
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	45	90.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	To a great extent	7.5		Some delay with T2.1 has impacted T2.2
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	To a great extent	7.5		Difficulty with hiring has somewhat delayed progress on T2.1, mitigated by adding non-specialist support
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		A student exchange and regular meetings are held by the two groups of the MPG
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		Meetings for T2.1 and T2.2 are regularly held and coordination of activity is strong
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	242.5	97.0%	

WP3 WP Leader Vito Trianni		Quality Compliance			Comments
		Answer	Score	Percentage	
Scope		0	47.5	95.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	To a great extent	7.5		Activities within T3.3 started earlier than foreseen. This should be documented somewhere.
Schedule		0	37.5	75.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Partially	5		Currently, partners have performed exploratory activities within the different tasks, following internal schedule. There is no shared planning for the different partners.
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	To a great extent	7.5		Activities within T3.1 cumulated some delay. A planning has been made during the consortium meeting in May 2024, and activities are currently ongoing.
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Partially	5		For individual partners, progress is monitored, but it would be necessary to scale monitoring up to the consortium level.
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		1	20	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	N/A	-		
Risk		1	27.5	91.7%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	To a great extent	7.5		There should be increased attention to dependencies with other tasks, to ensure timely delivery.
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	N/A	-		
Communication		0	42.5	85.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Partially	5		Meetings are organised on demand, when there is need to share information. Informal meetings are also held among students. A more systematic meeting organisation could be helpful to keep all partners up to date
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	To a great extent	7.5		WP meetings follow the frequency of consortium meetings. There could be stronger integration.
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		2	205	89.1%	

WP4 WP Leader Matti Häyry		Quality Compliance			Comments
		Answer	Score	Percentage	
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP5 WP Leader Ithai Rabinowitch		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	

WP6 WP Leader Elio Tuci		Quality Compliance			
		Answer	Score	Percentage	Comments
Scope		0	50	100.0%	
1	Are Tasks description up-to-date with the project requirements?	Yes	10		
2	Are the identified Deliverables in line with the project development?	Yes	10		
3	Are tasks and deliverables descriptions documented?	Yes	10		
4	Are objectives clearly identified and in line with project development?	Yes	10		
5	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Schedule		0	50	100.0%	
6	Is there an approved schedule for activities within single tasks?	Yes	10		
7	Are dependencies with external activities being respected?	Yes	10		
8	Are the tasks/activities duration estimation appropriate to this time?	Yes	10		
9	Are tasks status / % of completion being tracked and documented?	Yes	10		The OpenAire platform has been reactivated. The documents (reports and scientific documents) uploaded on Zenodo are successfully transferred into the project EU portal on the continuous reporting section.
10	Is the resource allocation appropriate?	Yes	10		
Cost		0	30	100.0%	
11	Are all costs and resources in line with the proposal?	Yes	10		
12	Are all costs related to the planned activities within each task correctly estimated?	Yes	10		
13	Are changes with respect to the project plan (if any) sufficiently documented?	Yes	10		
Quality		0	30	100.0%	
14	Is there a quality control methodology for Deliverables in place?	Yes	10		
15	Are outputs correctly maintained in a project repository?	Yes	10		
16	Have corrective actions been taken when required?	Yes	10		
Risk		0	40	100.0%	
17	Have new risks been identified and contingency measures planned?	Yes	10		
18	Are known risks continuously monitored?	Yes	10		
19	Are contingency measures for known risks continuously validated for applicability?	Yes	10		
20	Are risk mitigation plans being carried out?	Yes	10		
Communication		0	50	100.0%	
21	Is communication between partners involved in the WP satisfactory?	Yes	10		
22	Are there regular meetings for core WP activities?	Yes	10		
23	Is communication with partners involved in related WPs satisfactory?	Yes	10		
24	Do meetings and reports follow the planned frequency?	Yes	10		
25	Are meeting minutes distributed after meetings?	Yes	10		
		0	250	100.0%	